

ABSTRACT

Practice teaching is essential to the teacher-education curriculum because it helps student-teachers learn to become full-fledged educators. Through this, student-teachers experience becoming true teachers. Not only is this important in the teacher-education program because of the first-hand experiences it provides to student-teachers, but it is also an excellent opportunity for them to apply what they have learned regarding their profession and field of specialization. This phenomenological research study determines the challenges and difficulties of students engaged in practice teaching coming from various higher educational institutions from the fourth district of Iloilo province. Four themes have emerged during the phenomenological analysis of the data: Impressions of Face to Face Practice Teaching, Deployment of Student Teachers, Challenges and Difficulties of Student Teachers, Roles/Assignments Experienced, and Compliance during Practice Teaching.

Keywords: *New Normal, Practice Teaching, Fourth District, Iloilo*

INTRODUCTION

Education is essential in nation-building. It is a solid foundation for development. However, the quality of education depends on teachers' professional competence. More reliable curricula and learning experiences are needed to develop competent teachers. Above all, student-teachers must undergo rigorous learning experiences such as practice teaching.

Practice teaching is essential to the teacher-education curriculum because it helps student-teachers learn to become full-fledged educators. Through this, student-teachers experience becoming true teachers. Not only is this important in the teacher-education program because of the first-hand experiences it provides to student-teachers, but it is also an excellent opportunity for them to apply what they have learned regarding their profession and field of specialization.

Practice teaching is a unit course offered to Bachelor in Elementary Education (BEED) and Bachelor in Secondary Education (BSED) students who have completed field study 1-6. It is a part of the experiential learning courses of the New Teacher Education Curriculum according to Commission on Higher Education Memorandum No. 30, s. 2004. It aims to provide student teachers the chance to experience teaching in a virtual learning environment. It is done on-campus (in the laboratory school) or Off-campus (in the cooperating school).

Practice teaching is a full-time, full-day teaching experience undertaken by the student teachers as a requirement of the BEED or BSEd course. It requires a minimum of twelve (12) consecutive weeks of full-time attendance in the cooperating schools.

In the Philippines, student teaching is governed by CHED Memorandum Order No.11, series of 1999, which specifies the revised Policies and Standard for Teacher Education and CHED Memorandum No. 30, s. 2004. These policies focus on preparing globally competitive teachers who are in bed with Christian ideas, aspirations, and traditions of Philippine life and are sufficiently equipped with pedagogical knowledge and skills.

There are numerous types of research done in the field of education, but research on the plight of pre-service teachers during the new normal is far between; this led the researcher to study this phenomenon. Thus, this study aims to explore the present nature of student teaching practices, precisely the challenges, and difficulties experienced by the Higher Education institutions in the fourth district of Iloilo. Subsequently, to categorize and eventually find and develop themes.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. The research design chosen for this study is qualitative research, specifically, the Phenomenological approach. The researcher opted for data gathering involving interviewing participants, records, and documents.

Participants/Respondents. Since the face-to-face interview was prohibited because of the health protocols, a virtual conference to conduct the interview commenced after sending an email to the selected pre-service teachers of the seven Higher Education Institutions that offer teacher education programs in the fourth district of the province of Iloilo, the selection of whom was grounded on convenience sampling. Nonetheless, in most of the schools, out of five selected to answer most of them, only two responded to it. The participants were informed about the purpose of the study, and their

consent was obtained; in addition, it was notified that they could withdraw from the study at any time for any reason.

The name of the participants will not be mentioned throughout this research to protect their privacy. Each participant was named based on their school name. When extracting statements from their responses, expressions like ISCOF BN, ISCOF Dumangas, ISCOF BN, ISCOF Dingle, ISCOF San En, ISATU BN, and Passi City College are used.

Data Collection Procedure. After sending an email requesting the participants' consent to participate in the virtual interview, the researcher secured the interview questions. It involved three open-ended questions to uncover the student teaching practices of higher education institutions in the fourth district of the province of Iloilo that offer teacher education programs in the new normal.

Before gathering the necessary information and data for the study, the researcher first obtained the profile of schools in the fourth district of Iloilo. Then, the researcher determined the schools among the higher education institutions in the fourth district of Iloilo which offered teacher education programs. Then, through a written letter, the researcher asked permission from the college deans of the programs to conduct the research.

Data Analysis Procedure. The technique used in this study is a mix of narrative, document, and Thematic analysis.

Narrative inquiry records an individual's or small group's experiences, revealing the lived experience or particular perspective of that individual, usually primarily through an interview which is then recorded and ordered into a chronological narrative. Often, recorded a biography, life history, or older/ancient traditional story recording-oral history. It can reveal unique perspectives and a deeper understanding of a situation. Often giving voice to marginalized populations whose perspective is only sometimes sought. (Deakin University Library, 2022).

Document analysis is a form of qualitative research that uses a systematic procedure to analyze documentary evidence and answer specific research questions. Similar to other methods of analysis in qualitative research, document analysis requires repeated review, examination, and interpretation of the data to gain meaning and empirical knowledge of the construct being studied. Document analysis can be conducted as a stand-alone study or as a component of a more extensive qualitative or mixed methods study, where it is often used to triangulate findings gathered from another data source (e.g., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, surveys)(Bruce B. Frey, 2018).

Thematic analysis is a method of analyzing qualitative data. It is usually applied to texts, such as an interview or transcripts. The researcher closely examines the data to identify common themes-topics, ideas, and patterns of meaning that come up repeatedly (Jack Caulfield, 2019).

The data gathered from the questions were analyzed inductively following the steps suggested by Creswell (2007). The data were read and reread by the researcher. The researcher first selected one of the questions, thought about what was meant in the responses by the participant, and wrote it in two or three words.

Afterward, the coding process started. Following that, the researcher looked at his list of codes and tried to lessen the number of codes to 10-15 to avoid redundancy. Before commencing to develop themes from the codes, the researcher checked the codes and tried to decide on the discrepancies between the codes produced. Finally, themes were developed from the codes.

The researcher compiled five themes for analysis. The themes were coded as blue, yellow, green, maroon, and pink. Data considered within the theme's structure were shaded in the appropriate color in the transcript. Data collection was then incorporated into a table with the appropriate color.

Peer debriefing (Lincoln & Guba, 1985) was conducted to ensure trustworthiness in this research. The processes undergone in this study, from the employed research design to the data collection tool and analysis, were checked by a pre-service critic teacher, who, luckily, was the research adviser of the researcher. Moreover, member checking (Lincoln & Guba, 1985) was done by sharing the findings and their interpretations with the participants to ensure they reflected what they had in their minds so that their thoughts and ideas should prevail not by the researcher.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There were seven HEIs respondents in this study. The names of the actual participants will not be mentioned throughout this research to protect their privacy. Each participant was named based on their school name, and when extracting statements from their responses, expressions like ISCOF BN, ISCOF Dumangas, ISCOF BN, ISCOF Dingle, ISCOF San En, ISATU BN, Passi City College are used. Student teachers' of these respective schools were interviewed about their student teaching practices.

Data collected after the interview were analyzed and interpreted using a mix of narrative, document, and thematic analysis. The following themes were formulated after analyzing the data.

Theme 1: Impressions of Face-to-Face Practice Teaching

This refers to the expectations of student teachers before having their practice teaching and deployment.

Fears and concerns about how to practice teaching can be done now that the current educational system has been changed and that numerous community restrictions have been imposed as a result of the current epidemic have increased. As a result, practice teaching was given as much leeway as possible to follow protocols and provide as much experiential learning as possible.

In the case of the higher education institutions in the 4th district of Iloilo that offer teacher education programs, most of the student teachers expected that there would be changes in teaching-learning as they try to cope with the new normal.

Indeed, their practice teaching is significantly affected, as even their credibility as future educators. As ISAT-U BN and Passi City College mentioned, it was expected that there would be no face-to-face interaction for both student teachers and learners since most high schools are doing modular learning.

ISATU BN1: "...there are no students, and we cannot meet personally."

ISATU BN2: "...as student interns, we cannot be able to practice actual teaching; instead, we will do some sorting of modules and checking of learner's outputs. We cannot deal directly with the learners due to this pandemic..."

Passi City College: "...this would be difficult to practice because of not having an actual class with the students and can affect our future teachings."

Furthermore, despite this pandemic, student teachers were still expected to gain knowledge, strategies, and ideas for managing the classroom online or face-to-face from their cooperating teachers, critic teacher, and student teacher supervisors for them to be effective teachers. This was mentioned by ISCOF Main student teacher.

ISCOF Main1: '...I expect to be more knowledgeable enough to hone new skills in teaching and managing my own classroom; aside from that, our mentor can be focused on teaching us to be effective educators in the future by having virtual students and face-to-face classes.'

ISCOF Main2: Thinking that practice teaching would still be as effective as its purpose for student teachers in molding them to be better future educators..... I expect that there will be more control when it comes to classroom management.'

Aside from the strategies mentioned by the ISCOF Main Student Teacher, it was also important for student teachers to be more focused on how they will be able to connect virtually and facilitate learning for their learners in the midst of a pandemic after the official deployment as mentioned by ISCOF Dingle Campus.

ISCOF Dingle: My expectations for practice teaching in the new normal is how I will be able to connect with my students, given that we are facing a pandemic right now. How can I facilitate their learning and assess their learning?'

In preparing future teachers, it is expected that practice teaching will require adjustments for them as fourth-year students "to be called a student teacher," knowing that they were not fully equipped with the knowledge, experience, and mastery of the lesson they will soon be handling and teaching. As what ISCOF Dumangas mentioned:

ISCOF Dumangas: I will expect that practice teaching in a new normal will be a significant adjustment for us, the 4th year students.'

Face-to-face practice teaching was difficult, but participants like ISCOF San En looked at the positive side and concluded that there was still time to improve their selves and that it was an opportunity to be exposed to a different kind of learning environment. One that can still showcase their passion for the profession of teaching.

ISCOF San En: My expectations for practice teaching in the new normal is that it will be challenging, but I'm happy and excited because, finally, I will have an

excellent opportunity for myself to apply what I have learned regarding the teaching profession.

ISCOF BN added that it was expecting online classes in the new standard will be conducted. A student teacher had to be ready and familiar with the learning modalities that the school is implementing. To be prepared for the possible issues and problems that may occur when conducting online classes. Develop and use strategies that may be useful and provide experience as a future educator.

ISCOF BN: One of my expectations for practice teaching in the new normal is that conducting the online teaching wherein I am going to adjust to the needs of the students in terms of their connectivity to the internet, and at the same time, it's my first to handle college students before I deploy to my chosen school. In these times of my practice teaching journey, I can adapt and learn as well the strategies that will help me become a well-rounded teacher in the future.

Theme 2: Deployment of Student Teachers.

This refers to the official deployment of student teachers to schools after a Memorandum Agreement was entered with the DepEd. They are to be deployed either on- Campus (in the laboratory school) or off-Campus (in the cooperating school).

Practice teaching is a part of experiential learning courses of the New Teacher Education Curriculum pursuant to CHED Memorandum No. 30, S. 2004, which aims to provide the student teachers a chance to experience practice teaching in the virtual learning environment or natural classroom setting.

Teaching and learning experiences that take place outside of the confines of actual classroom walls have a range of benefits for both students and instructors. When students are asked to put into practice "in the real world" what they have theorized about from behind a desk, the result is a student-centric learning experience that enhances learning and fosters personal and social development (Larsen et al., 2017).

Thus, despite the time needing to be more, the student teacher coordinators and supervisors made their way to deploy their student teachers in-campus still as alternatives since off-campus was not possible for them. This was to make sure that they experienced such things as ISCOF San En, ISCOF Dumangas, ISCOF BN, ISCOF Dingle, and Passi City College mentioned.

ISCOF San En: "...despite the clock ticking for us student teachers, gladly we were deployed in-campus where we handle classes in lower years teaching our majored subjects...."

Passi City College: "...We have no practice teaching or deployment of student teachers because of this pandemic and protocols; what we did is just repost to school and work on our requirements set by our student teacher coordinator and prepare for Final Teaching demonstrations...."

ISCOF Dingle "...And since we have deployment on off campus, we were just deployed in-campus where we are tasked to teach the lower year level of our co-major...."

ISCOF Dumangas: "...So far, we do not have students teaching outside the school because of the risks of this pandemic deployment. As an alternative, we were only scheduled to report to school and assist our critique teacher and dean's office with paper works. So, it is understandable that we deploy in-campus only...."

Although for some schools, deployment was complex, in the case of ISATU BN, they were deployed off campus to their cooperating School at Barotac Nuevo National High School.

ISATU BN2: We were deployed off-campus and during our practice teaching at BNCHS.

Deployment for in-campus and off-campus went well for ISCOF Main, aside from in-campus deployment because their school has a laboratory school which is the Fisheries and Marine Science High School. They would eventually be deployed off campus to Barotac Comprehensive High School-Annex and Tiwi Elementary School to experience on-site training.

ISCOF Main2: "...Since we were deployed in-campus in our laboratory school and aside from that, our student teacher coordinator and supervisor are planning to have another off-campus deployment in the DepEd...."

Thus, the importance of deployment for practice teaching and having experience in an actual classroom setting is an excellent opportunity for student teachers.

Theme 3: Challenges and Difficulties of Student Teachers

This refers to the struggles experienced by the student teachers during their internship in-campus/off-campus.

During practice teaching, problems do occur along the way. Sariçoban (2010) found that the first problem in teaching is that student-teachers need to perform specific teaching skills that they are lacking. This problem occurs because there is a gap between the academic institution and the current teaching situation.

Some internal factors affect student-teachers attitudes in perceiving classrooms where they teach real students. Those factors include material preparation, teaching technique, classroom management, time management, and self-confidence problems, according to Priambodo (2012).

This is also one of the issues encountered by the ISCOF Dumangas. They admitted that the pandemic changed how they learn and interact with their learners. They were concerned about the learning they obtained during the pandemic and felt that they needed more time to be ready for deployment, especially in handling classes.

ISCOF Dumangas: "... we cannot deny the fact that we are not fully equipped with the knowledge and things that we need to apply if we are going to deploy in different secondary schools. Since we experienced this pandemic, the way we communicate and also learn has changed.."

The challenges and difficulties during the implementation of lockdowns and quarantine made them delay deployment because of the protocols that needed to be followed. Students were missing school activities and requirements that needed to be passed on time. Some Online classes were canceled due to the poor internet connection at their place. The changes in learning modalities from face-to-face to modular and online classes challenged student teachers with how they will be able to motivate their learners.

These issues make sense as ISCOF Main student teachers encountered the same thing.

ISCOF Main1: "...especially during lockdown because in our barangay we do not have signals that is why I missed and lost some of my activities...it is hard for me to force my students to attend online class and to urge them to submit their modules and activities we assigned. I hope that this matter will address because reminders are not enough to urge them to submit all the requirements...."

ISCOF Main2: "...some especially if I have assignments that need to be recorded/video. I find it hard because it really needs some time to finish. But overall, I have accomplished...the only change is that students will adopt the current situation wherein they still have to observe social distancing and wearing of face masks...."

ISCOF Main2: "...I have experienced difficulties in different things since we are doing modular and online classes... Some students in my class could not hear or learn better, especially since most of them did not have a good internet connection. It was a hindrance for them. Also, only a few of them entered our online class because their parents have difficulties funding them with load; some have no gadgets...."

ISCOF Dumangas, ISCOF BN, and Passi City College also pointed out the requirements. They encountered difficulties in working, processing, and preparing lesson plans and pre/final demonstration teaching, although they still needed to be deployed in DepEd.

ISCOF Dumangas: "...our difficulties encountered with regards to the requirements are on how we prepare for our final demo teaching."

ISCOF BN: "...Especially in completing our grades and processing some papers."

Passi City College: "...Even though we have no OJT in any schools still, it is not easy to comply with all those requirements, plus we have to have our duty or reporting on campus."

Meanwhile, practice teaching was also a source of stress for the student teachers. As ISATU BN mentioned, they encountered the challenges of a teacher. There were too many tasks to do, like

checking and sorting modules/outputs, and especially completing/computing grades, managing the learners virtually, and preparing lessons.

ISATU BN1: "...I already experience the hard work of the teachers, especially when it comes to the sorting and checking of modules... I have encountered difficulties complying with requirements, especially in making lesson plans, weekly plans, summative tests, and how to handle students in a group chat and teach them virtually."

ISATU BN2: "... There are too many tasks to do like, for example, sorting out of modules, checking of summative/formative assessment of learners as well as their outputs and many more but with better self-discipline and time management, everything was done properly and successfully...."

The presence and guidance of the student teacher coordinator, supervisor, and critical teacher is an excellent factor when having practice teaching.

Ogonor and Badmus (2013) mentioned that mentor teachers play an essential role in the student's practicum. The purpose of a teaching practicum program, among others, is to provide trainees or student-teachers with the opportunity to utilize the various teaching methods in actual classrooms/school conditions under the supervision of competent and experienced teachers.

This statement was the issue faced by ISCOF Dingle and ISCOF San En. They stated that aside from the tasks and responsibilities that were given. Their cooperating teacher or critic teacher was only sometimes in school since, in the midst of the pandemic, they were obliged to have their work from home and follow the skeletal system implemented in their school. At the same time, student-teachers were supposed to communicate and work with their mentor teachers since they have more experiences, skills, and knowledge that would be very useful for the student-teachers.

Another thing that was added to their list of difficulties for ISCOF Dingle is their health and safety, where they need to follow the minimum health protocols set by the LGU and the IATF.

ISCOF Dingle: "...it is quite challenging to adjust, and it is risky on my part. We need to follow the safety measures to protect ourselves from covid...It is not easy on my part to ask questions to my subject teacher, having that there following the skeletal system or working from home. Which is very hard to communicate with them, especially if there is no signal."

ISCOF San En: "... some of the teachers work from home; that is why we cannot directly transact with them in a timely manner."

These concerns about the challenges and difficulties encountered by Student teachers, proved by (Nasir & Zafar, 2018), stated that student teachers had challenges in managing their class time. That is, distributing appropriate time for each activity, wasting too much time checking students' homework, giving instructions, and taking attendance.

Theme 4: Roles/Assignments Experienced

This theme refers to the tasks/responsibilities given to the student teachers upon deployment in/off-campus.

Practice teaching requires total commitment and dedication from the student teacher. As such, he/she is expected to immerse himself/herself in doing some specific responsibilities expected to pre-service.

Fung & Chow (2002) stated, "Mentor or cooperating teachers take the role of reflection facilitator by posing examples, analyzing and interpreting teaching practice, challenging student-teachers for value justifications and encouraging positive dispositions in teaching ."The mentor must give some input to student-teachers and give guidance to accomplish tasks such as administration, disciplinary procedure, and cooperative working with other teachers (Wallace, 1991).

During the internship, student teachers were not able to hold classes virtually and practice their skills in teaching because the school where they were deployed adopted the modular kind of learning. What they were made to do was check and sort modules, prepare for tests and exams, and compute grades just like ISATU BN.

ISATU BN2: "...we will not be able to practice our skills in teaching since most schools adopt modular learning. And lastly, the only thing we can show our skills in teaching is through teaching demonstration...especially with the requirements in school like our portfolio; there are too many requirements to comply with, just like the pictures of the facilities in cooperating school, the sample of letter to the parents, Home visitation form and more. Also, we have to make 6 lesson plans every quarter and the weekly home learning plan. Nevertheless, with these

requirements, I could not comply it within one night still, as long as I am encouraged and motivated to work, I can comply with everything before the deadline."

On the other hand, ISCOF Main stated that punctuality, going to duty on time, being involved in any activities in school, and being mindful of the duties and responsibilities assigned by the coordinator, supervisor, and cooperating teacher was their most common difficulty. Since they were deployed in the laboratory school, they had the opportunity to hold classes in a virtual class with the guidance of their critic and cooperating teacher.

ISCOF Main3: "Be punctual, Report daily for a full school day, become involved in activities and functions carried out by the classroom teacher, and assume responsibilities designated by the mentor teacher...I spent much time preparing each lesson plan or ppt to present. I researched different ways to present the information for each lesson. I looked for activities that my students would enjoy, and I made sure that I had all of the materials and other things that I needed before class started."

Furthermore, ISCOF BN said they were assigned to sort modules and handle classes virtually for lower-year college students.

ISCOF BN: "...My cooperating teacher assigned me to do some photocopying, filed it, and listed the names of her students way back 2017 up to the present. She also assigned me to take over her speech and stage arts class on her BSED-English 1 A and B students...."

ISCOF Dumangas was just assigned to report to the school and assist their supervisor and dean in school-related work.

ISCOF Dumangas "... What just we do is only assigned to report at school, assist, and do stuff in the dean's office...."

While ISCOF Dingle was deployed in-campus, they were just assigned to check and sort the modules of their fellow lower-year college students.

ISCOF Dingle: "...We need to follow the safety measures to protect ourselves from covid. It was fun that I was able to distribute modules and get along with the parents of my students...."

Theme 5: Compliance during Practice Teaching

This refers to the requirements required for student teachers before and during internship or practice teaching.

It was mentioned by ISATU BN that with regards to their compliance, they have Pre-Internship Requirements, application letter for practice teaching, practice teaching agreement form, permit to enroll, resume, photocopy of vaccination card (fully vaccinated), waiver, and medical certificates.

For Post- internship requirements, they will be required to a daily Time record, journal (Daily Log), performance evaluation form, portfolio, lesson plan, 6 lesson plans (3rd quarter), 6 lesson plans (4th Quarter), teaching demonstration (Thursday and Friday), and they had to report to school (Monday-Wednesday).

ISATU BN2: "Our requirements are attached to the file...At first, it was tiring and difficult but later on, we got used to it and worked efficiently and collaboratively with our cooperating teachers..."

Although ISCOF San En could not deploy off-campus, they still stated their requirements for the in-campus training. These include the Pre-Requirements; Assessment of Grades, Certificate of Enrolment (indicating student is officially enrolled in the OJT/internship, Medical Certificate, Curriculum Vitae or Personal Data Sheet (Form9), 1 picture (1X1), Moral Character Certificate and Barangay/Police Clearance, Pre-Internship Seminar Attendance/Certificate of Completion, Signed and Notarized Parent's Consent Form (local) Affidavit of Undertaking (Form12, Signed Student Internship Form (form 8), Signed THE and Student-intern's Internship Agreement Form (Form 10), Signed Internship General Agreement Form (Form 11)Machine Copy/Electronic Copy of Vaccination card, Machine copy/Electronic Copy of Phil Health ID.

For their final requirement, they needed to have Observation of Classes, Pre-Observation and Post-Observation Conferences, Class Routines (Orientation), Preparation of Instructional Materials, Class Activities, Assessment Practices, Demonstration Teaching, School Forms, and Networking and Linkages(online professional activities, local and international)

ISCOF San En: "...So far, lesson planning, classroom management & teaching demonstration and many more, screenshot attached below."

While Passi City College required their student teachers to have minimum compliance since they were only deployed in-campus, the Journal, Students Portfolio, 400hrs flexible training internship, and Preliminary and Final Demonstration.

Passi City College: "...because we just deployed in-campus, where we only have to assist our supervisor and cooperating teacher. They are just required to have these requirements. Journal, students portfolio, 400hrs flexible training internship, and preliminary and final demonstration."

ISCOF Dumangas, ISCOF Dingle, and ISCOF BN had the exact requirements and could not deploy off-campus. Nevertheless, they were required to accomplish these requirements; the pre-orientation program, profile of the cooperating teacher, attendance orientation program, checked lesson Plans, Student Teaching Notebook, student teaching portfolio, and narrative report of pre-Service teacher.

ISCOF Dumangas: we failed to have our deployment off-campus, so to fill in the gap, we have our internship in-campus that is expected to complete these requirements afterward. First, the pre-orientation program, profile of the cooperating teacher, attend orientation program, checked lesson Plans, Student Teaching Notebook, student teaching portfolio, narrative report of pre-Service teacher."

ISCOF Dingle: Pre-orientation program, the profile of the cooperating teacher, attend orientation program, checked lesson Plans, Student Teaching Notebook, student teaching portfolio, narrative report of pre-Service teacher."

ISCOF BN: "...as our coordinator said, we have only to comply with the Pre-orientation program, profile of the cooperating teacher, attend orientation program, checked lesson Plans, Student Teaching Notebook, student teaching portfolio, narrative report of pre-Service teacher."

ISCOF's Main requirements were similar to other campuses like the ISCOF Dumangas, Dingle, and BN. The only difference was that there was an additional requirement for them, the neuro-psycho test, and aside from handling classes in high school, they still had to report to school (by major).

ISCOF Main: "...here on the main campus, we need to comply with the signed internship general agreement form (Form 11) and student intern's internship agreement form (Form 10), pre-Internship seminar attendance/certificate of completion, the profile of the cooperating teacher, attend an orientation program, checked lesson plans, medical certificates, neuro psycho test, student teaching portfolio, narrative report of pre-service teacher, duty on school (by central).

This study attempted to investigate the student teaching practices of higher education institutions in the 4th district of Iloilo. This study sought to answer the following:

What are the student teaching practices of higher education institutions in the 4th district of Iloilo?

Some might wonder what the pre-service teachers do in the new normal. They need an internship program where pre-service teachers will be raised and implemented. Pre-service teachers must experience the actual classroom setting to apply what they have learned.

In the case of the student teaching of higher education institutions in the 4th district of Iloilo, student teachers are deployed in-off campus. This occurs after the Memorandum agreement between CHED and DepEd and after submitting all the requirements as stated by ISCOF BN.

Through this, ISAT U BN, ISCOF Main, and ISCOF Dumangas, pre-service teachers were able to have their practice teaching for the required time and days. Some had the chance to work on papers. Others handled classes, and some were assigned to the sorting, printing, and checking of modules.

How did the pre-service teachers cope with the situation?

Despite all the sectors adjusting to the new normal, the pre-service still manages to go with it. All Student-teacher supervisors were challenged in preparing the student teaching of all the pre-service teachers. Some Schools that offer teacher education programs in higher education institutions still

manage to deploy their pre-service teachers off-campus, just like ISATU BN Campus and ISCOF MAIN CAMPUS.

Others were deploying their student teachers inside the campus or what we call in-campus as an alternative. This is to ensure that the pre-service teacher will be exposed to and experience what people do under Department of Education, as expressed by ISAT U BN and ISCOF Dumangas.

Being a teacher means taking on many roles besides the deliverer of content. We have many responsibilities and take on numerous roles in our schools through activities, committees, or anything that enables us to build a sense of community in our classrooms and our schools. However, one role equally as important as being a teacher is being a learner and, more importantly, being a learner for life. Thus, pre-service teachers must be honed and be prepared because the future is in their hands as makers of all Professions and professionals.

Why did they encounter these difficulties?

Upon reviewing the profiles of each school, the researcher found out that aside from the pandemic that hinders and limits the pre-service teacher's duties and responsibilities, the location, population, courses offered by the school, plus internet connection or signal within the area, have excellent factors that contribute to the challenges and difficulties encountered by the pre-service teachers which caused them sometimes to the situation where they cannot be able to connect and communicate with their cooperating teacher and supervisor. These are experienced mainly by some HEIs like ISCOF BN, ISCOF Dingle, ISCOF San En, and ISCOF Main.

Some of these schools, like the ISATU BN, ISCOF Main, ISCOF Dingle, and ISCOF San En, are located far away from their "banwa" which makes it challenging to travel if these student teachers need to process with regards to their school-related requirements.

Another factor that adds problems to the pre-service teachers is the requirements being required before and during the internship, as stressed by most participants. The researcher also found out that some schools still followed the required requirements by the CHED, and some adjusted their requirements to go along with the new normal.

Lastly, the task is too much for the pre-service teacher, a misconception sometimes that once students are now in pre-service teaching, they have to do all things that the real teachers do. This sometimes causes trouble for pre-service teachers because of a lack of guidance from cooperating teachers and the student-teacher supervisor; ISAT U BN and ISCOF Main prove this.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the researcher came up with the following conclusions:

First, Student teachers in the fourth of Iloilo were able to have their student internship program either in or off-campus despite the pandemic. This is possible not just because of the effort of their student teacher coordinators and supervisors but also as mandated by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED).

According to CHED (2020): "The need to shift from residential or face-to-face teaching to flexible learning in higher education and learning delivery modalities in basic education to ensure the health, safety, and security of the teachers, students, pre-service teachers, and other stakeholders during the time of the pandemic is fundamental."

This resulted in different decisions made by the higher education institutions in the fourth district of Iloilo on how they will implement the Student teachers' practice of teaching

ISCOF Main was the only higher education institution in the fourth district with a teacher education program that successfully implemented the deployment of their student teachers both in-campus (in the laboratory school) and Off-Campus (in the cooperating schools), which is around the campus only.

Secondly, the researcher also concluded that another situation that challenged the student-teachers was that, in reality, student-teachers are also often seen as replacement teachers. Mentor-teachers often force their ideas on these novice teachers based on what they have experienced rather than let the student-teachers experience their problems with their solutions. Furthermore, school students often see student-teachers as temporary teachers and thus take them for granted, which adds stress to some practice teachers.

This was proven by Sarıçoban (2010), it was found that the first problem in teaching is that student-teachers need to perform specific teaching skills that they are lacking. This problem occurs because there is a gap between the academic institution and the current teaching situation.

Since the participants had to adapt and adopt the learning delivery modality of their school and their cooperating school, some schools still followed the requirements required of student teachers; some were adjusted to fit the new normal. Furthermore, teaching experiences were limited to almost three hours out of the prescribed 18-week practice teaching duration. Hence, their knowledge of teaching essentials, including lesson planning, students' discipline management, and students' differences, needed to be reinforced. Also, this pandemic intensified personal-inherent challenges like allowances and stress management.

As mentioned, the conduct of the teaching internship at the height of the pandemic served as an avenue for practice teachers to learn and improve themselves with many new skills and self-discovery. Their teaching skills might have yet to be fully enhanced, but they have acquired soft skills equally important in succeeding in teaching or the workplace in general.

Additionally, in preparing future teachers, they must be equipped with the knowledge and skills integral to being a teacher, such as a lesson preparation, student discipline management and lesson development, and various teaching strategies that suit the differences of the students.

To this end, they must be trained in their junior years of college so that practice teaching will no longer be a period of acquisition but of practice and reinforcement. By the time the students enroll in various professional education courses, they must experience that all of their learned concepts, such as individual differences, multiple intelligences, objectives formulation, and teaching approaches and strategies, can be applied in a classroom setting in the new normal. It has been a big challenge for courses with laboratory and practical exercises, especially for student teachers, to continue and ensure their sufficient knowledge, skills, and readiness in the workplace despite the pandemic. In this study, it was proven that the pandemic posed challenges to practice teachers. This is proof that despite the challenges, higher education institutions in the fourth district of Iloilo that have professional education programs are still learning and adjusting to cope and continue their practice teaching amid the pandemic or what we called the new normal.

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